
ANALYSIS OF MICRO-FINANCING AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Aimed at evaluating the nature of interrelationships between Nigeria's economic growth and micro-Financing allocations to classified sectors of economic activity, this study employs Augmented Dickey-Fuller Johansen's Co-integration, Error Correction Model and Standard Pair-Wise Granger Causality tests. Data was sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin over the period of 1992 to 2014. The results reveal stationarity of the time series data and significant long run relationship among the study variables. No significant causalities are found between Nigeria's gross domestic product and microcredit allocations to agriculture/forestry and other mining/quarrying sectors. On the other hand, micro-Financing allocated to other manufacturing/food processing as well as real estate/construction are found to witness significant causalities with Nigeria's gross domestic product. The causalities flow from gross domestic product to micro-Financing allocated to these sectors. On the whole, Nigeria's GDP and micro-Financing allocated to transport/general commerce sector are found to have significant bi-directional causality thereby, mutually promoting and reinforcing each other. The study concludes that microcredit operations are exerting enlarged influence in Nigeria by becoming significant in increasing number of sectors and recommends improvements in micro-Financing and microcredit products which must meet sector specific needs of enterprise. Finally, reduction in tax and levy rates are recommended in favour of operating microcredit institutions in order to minimize their operating costs and boost their capacities to contribute more to Nigeria's economic growth.

Keywords: Analysis, Micro-financing, Economic growth process

1.0 Introduction

The benefits of financial institutions in the process of economic growth of developed and developing economies derives from their key roles in the financial intermediation process. Ajie et al (2006) describe the process of financial intermediation as that concerned with the mechanism and techniques of mobilizing saved financial resources from the surplus saving units in the economy and efficient allocation of same to the needy sectors, thereby, funding investment activities and ultimately, economic growth. The classical studies of Schumpeter (1934), Goldsmith (1969), McKinnon (1973) as well as Shaw (1973, 1976) articulate the potential roles of financial institutions in the economic growth process even under liberalized and repressed regimes. However, Schumpeter (1934) specifically views financial institutions as typical handmaids to industry and argues that financial institutions significantly function in a demand-following manner. The novelty in Schumpeterian theory however, emanates from the point that it views financial institutions, especially the banking system as endowed with the capacity to create unlimited credit, which is a prerequisite for funding the ever expanding innovative enterprise. Generally, the above studies provide basis to contend that significant interrelationships prevail between financial and economic growth and in many economies, they could significantly support and/or promote themselves in the process of economic growth.

At policy level, Adeyemi (2007) and Agene (2011) again, observe that Nigerian government initiated several actions and programmes to enhance the active poor's access to micro-financing. These actions include establishment and funding of key development financial institutions to address the microcredit needs of the citizenry. They include the Nigerian Agricultural Co-operative and Rural Development Bank, which addresses the credit needs of registered farmers and other rural based microcredit needs of related entrepreneurs. There also, exists the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme directly under the supervision of the Central Bank of Nigeria. It functions to mitigate the varied forms of agricultural risks to which farmers are exposed in the agricultural production cycle. Of significance also, is the establishment of the Peoples Bank in 1989 which was to additionally focus on the various non-urban and associated small-scale credit needs of the active poor. Also in existence, are diversified forms of state government supervised microcredit schemes that address the needs of micro-financing. They include various state induced co-operatives as well as other multiple micro enterprise agencies supervised by state government parastatals and ministries.

Micro-financing explains credits issued by specialized financial institutions such as co-operative unions in Nigeria, previous community banks and present day microfinance banks which are basically aimed at leveraging the economic pursuits of the active poor. In this respect, Adeyemi (2007) observes that Nigerian government has been favourably disposed to the creation of viable microcredit institutions and associated environments in order to provide the active poor with significant financial leverage which in the nearest future, will improve both their financial well bring, employment opportunities and potential contributions to national economic growth. Within the framework of this study therefore, micro-financing are conceived according to Agene (2011), as those comparatively smaller values of credit facilities provided by the specialized financial institutions to the micro entrepreneurs on individual or group basis, principally under anticipated income/cash flow conditions in place of the conventionally securitized credits disbursed by the conventional commercial banks in accordance with the dictates of real bills doctrine or commercial loan theory.

For continuity in terms of provision of micro-financing for the active poor under a deregulated framework, the government initiated the community banking programme. In this direction, the emerging community banks were privately owned and also, expected to confine their financial

intermediation activities within their operational environments. Unfortunately, the community banks' operations were found to have followed conventional commercial banking credit policy patterns as noted by Danda (2007) in terms of their observed preference to lend to the more juicy general commerce sector at the expense of micro enterprise in general and agricultural sector in particular. The community banking scheme soon witnessed significant deterioration in their asset quality over the years. In this direction, Nnamdi and Nwakanma (2011) observe that the government acting through the Central Bank of Nigeria, took exigent measures to reform the community banking framework. These reform measures paved way for the emergence of the microfinance banking programme in Nigeria. By 31' Dec. 2006, all operating community banks were directed to transform to microfinance banks with significantly enhanced capital base requirements. The core objective still remains a strategic maximization of the economic potentials and financial independence of the active poor through deliberate financial inclusion programmes.

The moribund Rural Banking scheme which prevailed between 1982 and 1991 in Nigeria represents another significant government led attempt to co-opt the operating commercial banks into the micro-financing scheme. Against the backdrop that operating commercial banks' credit policies and associated conditions for credit approval were highly discriminatory with respect to the enterprising poor, Olashore (1983) argues that rural banking scheme represents a significant effort through which the federal government compelled the private sector-led commercial banking industry to bear part of the cost of national development. To enforce the policy, the study further observes that the Central Bank of Nigeria compelled operating commercial banks to prioritize credit facilities to the preferred sectors with significant emphasis on agriculture and other small scale indigenous enterprises at the risk of serious sanctions. In addition, the operating commercial banks had to meet with the stringent condition of establishing specified number of rural branches as a prerequisite for approval of requests for the establishment of new urban branches. Following the deregulation of Nigerian economy which commenced in 1986, further provisions were made for a more effective market-led economy. This witnessed the abolition of statutory allocation of credits and compelled location of bank branches in the rural enclaves. Substantially, there were conflicting opinions among practicing bankers on the profitability of rural branches. While Umesi (1981) argues that most rural branches of banks were operating at a loss because of very low activities, Ibene (1981) observes that banks have no reasons to complain on the scheme. If they should complain at all the study argues, their complaint basically derives from the fact that they did not only understand, but failed to appreciate the market dictates of the rural economy. The study urges the banks to understand the vital need for marketing of financial services products and core relationship management as opposed to their usual arm-chair approach to business in the urban enclaves. In the same vein, Umoh (1984) finds it difficult to reconcile the huge corporate profits declared by operating banks against their complaints on the rural banking scheme.

Studies have provide compelling evidences to confirm conflicting results as to the nature of empirical relationships between bank credits and economic growth of nations; Aliero et al (2013), Murty et al (2012), Nwakanma et al (2014), as well as Nuno (2012). Unfortunately, irrespective of the fact that the conventional commercial banks continuously seek to expand their credit portfolios in response to demands of business enterprises, the active poor have significantly been discriminated against. This as usual, is traced to the fact that commercial banks would under normal circumstances, only lend on the basis of matching principles, preferably to short term profitable and self liquidating investments duly securitized. In this connection, Yunus (2003) as well as Helms (2006) observe that irrespective of these discriminatory tendencies, micro enterprises significantly prevail in diversified sectors of economic activity in many developing and developed nations. To this extent, microcredit operations have continued to contribute not

only to employment generation in many developing economies but also, to the growth of economic activities in diversified sectors of these economies.

This study hinges on the premise that there is a growing interest in microcredit operations evidenced by increasing literature on the subject. There are also, increased government actions inclusive of periodic reforms of the agencies and institutions that often serve as vehicles for microcredit policy implementation. However, irrespective of the diversity of findings on the nature of relationships between microcredit operations and aggregated economic growth of nations, the studies reviewed so far fall short of any significant attempt to evaluate this relationship with respect to the various sectors of economic enterprise in order to empirically examine the subject on sectoral basis in Nigeria.

While the general objective of this study is to examine the nature of interrelationships which prevail between sectoral micro-financing allocations and Nigeria's economic growth, specifically, this study will attempt to; (i) analyze the nature of prevailing long-run relationship between Nigeria's economic growth and microcredit allocations to the various sectors, of classified economic activity and (ii) the extent to which each of these micro-financing allocations to various sectors of economic activity and Nigeria's economic growth do promote, support and/or reinforce each other in the light of recent data. These issues therefore, constitute the core problem of this study.

Discoveries of this study will hopefully, contribute not only to the evolving empirical literature on the subject of micro-financing operations in Nigeria, but in addition, they are expected to offer valuable basis for improved policy actions in the interest of the operators, active poor and the regulators. Having provided a general review of the subject, the rest of this study is divided into four distinct sections. While section 1 holds as above, section 2 provides the theoretical framework and review of related literature on the subject. Section 3 offers the methodology adopted for the study while section 4 presents the analysis and results. Finally, section 5 provides the discussions, conclusions and relevant policy recommendations.

Conceptual Clarification

Analysis: Analysis explains the breaking down of complex information, data or systems into smaller, more manageable parts to examine, and understand, their relationships, patterns and meanings. In a more simplified explanation, analysis involves identification, evaluation, examination and interpretation of activities. Analysis could be qualitative, quantitative, critical and comparative analysis. It is basically an important skill found in the body of studies such as science, business, social science, humanities, health care engineering, finance, marketing and many more. Analysis helps in many ways not limited to: (a) gain insights and understanding (b) identify patterns and trends, (c) make informed decisions (d) solve problems and challenges and (e) develop new ideas perspectives.

Micro-finance: this is a type of financial service that provides small loans, savings other financial products to individuals or groups who lack access to traditional banking services. Micro-finance institutions (MFIS) offer a range of services not limited to:

- (a) Micro-loans which involves loans from N5, 000 to N50, 000 to support entrepreneurship, small businesses or personal needs.
- (b) Savings accounts: to secure accessible savings options for individuals and groups.
- (c) Micro-insurance: these are insurance products tailored to the needs of low income individuals or groups.
- (d) Money transfers: these are services that enable to send and receive money domestically and internationally.

Objectives of Micro-financing

Micro-finance is a help to individuals and organizations aimed at performing the following functions not limited to:

- (a) **Promote Financial Inclusion:** Micro-finance provides access to financial services for underserved populations such as low-income individuals, women and rural communities.
- (b) **Foster entrepreneurship development:** it supports small businesses and entrepreneurship, contributes to economic growth, development and job creation.
- (c) **Improve Livelihood:** Micro-finance enhances the overall well-being of individuals and families by providing access to financial serves and promoting economic stability.

Potential gains of Micro-finance

It is believed that well managed micro-finance activities have the potential to reduce the following in the economy:

- (i) **Poverty Reduction:** by providing access to financial services, micro-finance can help individuals and families break the cycle of poverty.
- (ii) **Empower women:** micro-finance has been shown to have positive impact on women's economic empowerment and social status.
- (iii) **Promote Economic growth and development:** Micro-finance has the potential to contribute to economic growth and development by supporting entrepreneurs, job creation and income generation.

Challenges of Micro-finance

Challenges bedeviling micro-financing are not limited to the following:

1. **High interest Rate:** Micro-finance institutions usually charge high interest rates sometimes above CBN set interest rates as to cover cost and manage risks.
2. **Debt traps:** the borrowers may be trapped in debt cycles when they are unable to service their loans.
3. **Regulatory challenges:** Micro-finance institutions (MFS) often operate in an unclear regulatory environments that are restrictive. Micro-finance has the potential to make positive impact on the lives of millions of people world-wide. However, it requires careful management regulations, and oversight to ensure realization of its benefits.

The Process of Economic Growth

The Supply-Leading Finance Theory

One of the celebrated theories that lend support to micro-financing operations and their accelerated embracement by national governments is the supply-leading finance theory. According to Robinson (2001), supply-leading finance theory basically contends that rural economic growth with particular emphasis on agricultural pursuits could be enhanced through the financial system through provision of subsidized credits and other agricultural inputs in advance of the demand for farm products. The theory hinges on the fact that most of the farmers hardly save and so, could not afford to procure the needed agricultural inputs, as well as pay the commercial costs of banks credits. The theory was later expanded to cover all micro enterprises, agricultural and non-agricultural and provides a significant basis for massive

government embracement of green revolution in many developing economies including Nigeria in the 1960s and 1970s.

However, supply-leading finance theory is criticized on the basis of the following, (i) its wide embracement could create room for continued credit subsidies, (ii) continued credit subsidies could consequently, provide room for the government to finance micro enterprises at a higher cost, (iii) it may provide opportunities for some influential groups within the local environment to divert the subsidized credit resources and (iv) these scholars further argue that credit subsidies will at macro level, have the effect of suppressing savings mobilization, investments and institutional sustainability, because the subsidized cost of lending does not reflect the true cost of funds in the economy in view of efficiency of investment allocations.

Empirical Literature

Scholars have provided compelling evidences relating micro-financing to economic growth.

Organization of Data and Methodology

Data and Variable Description

The organized data for this study were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria’s Statistical Bulletin over the period 1992 to 2014 (23 years). The data set consists of the yearly values of the outstanding micro-financing allocated and/or disbursed to the various classified sectors of economic activity in Nigeria in accordance with Central Banks’ classification of same. The annual values of gross domestic product at market prices are adopted because they are like sectoral allocation of credit values, historical in nature. For all intents and purposes these prices represent the market prices which consumers pay for goods and services at each point in time over the period of analysis. On the whole, the data employed covers only community banking and micro finance phases of the micro-financing scheme. This is attributed to the fact that published and organized data are not available on sectoral classification of micro-financing prior to the community banking scheme as shown in table 1 below:

Table 1: Allocation of Microcredits to Economic sectors of Activity in Nigeria and Gross Domestic Product over the Period 1992 – 2014 (₦’M)

Year	Gross Domestic Product at Current Market Price (GDP)	Microcredit Facilities to Agriculture and Forestry (FAF)	Microcredit Facilities to other Mining and Quarrying (FMQ)	Microcredit facilities to Manufacturing and Food Processing (FMF)	Microcredit Facilities to Real Estate and Construction (FRC)	Microcredit facilities to Transport and General Commerce(FT C)
1992	909,750	29.50	3.70	19.90	14.60	45.60
1993	113,220	123.20	5.70	129.60	47.50	280.00
1994	1,457,130	155.40	32.20	201.00	34.90	513.80
1995	2,991,940	98.60	17.90	124.80	102.60	575.70
1996	4,135,810	229.40	17.60	155.40	92.70	695.00
1997	4,300,210	367.40	28.50	200.00	105.20	729.90
1998	4,101,030	962.70	31.00	299.40	67.10	1042.70
1999	4,799,970	1007.20	27.00	293.50	71.90	1447.80
2000	6,850,230	1248.35	33.46	363.77	89.11	1794.44

2001	7,055,300	447.37	11.99	130.36	31.94	643.08
2002	7,984,400	1467.71	39.34	427.69	104.77	2109.77
2003	10,136,400	3389.27	90.86	987.64	241.95	4871.91
2004	11,673,600	3865.58	103.62	1126.44	275.95	5556.58
2005	14,735,320	9704.91	260.16	2828.03	692.79	13950.33
2006	18,709,800	505.23	449.33	491.98	2554.43	5078.32
2007	20,940,910	701.90	624.14	683.39	3548.24	7054.05
2008	24,665,240	3354.30	412.40	2006.33	2139.15	23962.48
2009	25,225,140	4736.90	569.70	2275.70	2421.10	28314.20
2010	29,498,160	5102.90	520.40	2172.90	2257.40	25975.80
2011	30,872,700	4917.10	571.00	2912.50	1754.80	38275.80
2012	40,544,000.10	5056.80	524	2482.60	4222.30	59774.30
2013	42,396,000.80	4803.10	603.30	2937.30	2612.00	53409.50
2014	89,043,000.62	7,735.7	187.10	3156.50	5486.50	58821.80
2015	91,064,000.71	7,736.8	54.300	3157.51	5487.51	58923.81
2016	91,085000.84	8,934.5	467.43	3258.52	5587.52	58024.82
2017	93,091,000.86	8,973.6	236.76	3259.51	5688.53	58024.84
2018	96,094000.87	8,975.7	849.44	3359.3	5689.54	6192.85
2019	96,094,000.88	9,866.3	8794.5	3369.1	5690.55	6194.87
2020	98,096,000.88	9,569.4	8874.4	3362.4	5791.56	6295.88
2021	98,096,000.89	9768.9	8875.5	34.63.3	5892.57	6496.89
2022	99,098,000.89	10,678.7	8876.3	5464.4	5801.58	6698.89
2023	99,098,000.96	10,589.7	8976.2	5568.5	5893.61	6899.91

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria, Statistical Bulletin (Various Years).

While the gross domestic product (GDP) serves as the relevant indicator for economic growth, the outstanding microcredits allocated to various sectors of classified economic activity serve as the contributions of the private sector driven microcredit agencies in leveraging Nigeria's economy. In this vein, several empirical studies including Aliero et al (2013), Murtey et al (2012), Nwakanma et al (2014) as well as N uno (2012) have employed the gross domestic product as a good measure of economic performance with valuable results. Further, since the microcredit programmes under consideration are private sector driven, it becomes expedient to assert in accordance with the studies of Demetriades and Hussein (1996) as well as Crowley (2008) that private sector credits are perceived as more effective and of greater influence on the economy since they are disbursed under more stringent credit conditions. Consequently, it is contended that the annual values of these sectorally disbursed credits and Nigeria's gross domestic product constitute objective basis for prediction of the nature of long run relationship as well as nature and directions of causality that empirically prevail between microcredit sectoral distributions and economic growth in Nigeria.

3.2 Specification of Analytical Tools and Tests

Given the stated objectives of this study, this subsection for purpose of greater clarity, is subdivided as follows;

3.2.1 Stationarity Tests

Stationarity tests are conventionally executed in order to ascertain the unit root properties of applicable time series data and ultimately, avoid spurious estimates. Maddala (2007) as well as Gujarati and Porter (2009) elucidate unit root procedure as shown in equation (1):

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum$$

The decision rule for unit root test is that if the calculated value of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test statistic is higher in absolute terms compared to those of the Mckinnon's critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, then the null hypothesis H_0 will be rejected and the alternate accepted. This implies non-existence of a unit root and a confirmation of the suitability of the time series data for application in Johansen's co-integration. The converse would also hold for rejection. On the whole, if the null hypothesis fails to be rejected, further differencing would be conducted on the differenced variants of the time series data in order to achieve stationarity based on modification of the fundamental expression indicated in equation (1) above as follows.

Given this differenced form in equation (2), the implicated hypotheses for testing become;

3.2.2 Johansen's Cointegration Test

To evaluate the extent of long run relationship that prevails in time series variables within a multivariate frame work, the Johansen's co-integration technique is employed. In a dynamic model with stationary disturbances and a defined order of integration say n , the set of those variables are said to be integrated of order n also. Brooks (2009) observes that within the Johansen's multivariate co-integration framework, if a set of g variables prevails where g consists of at least two variables, it implicates the setting up of a Vector Auto Regression (VAR) model which contains the g variables in their first differenced form inclusive of defined lags of the form $k - 1$ with an associated matrix of T -coefficient. Accordingly, the Johansen's co-integration for a multivariate framework with defined g number variables is expressed below in equation (3) as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = \lambda y_{t-k} + T_1 \Delta y_{t-1} + T_2 \Delta y_{t-2} + \dots + T_{k-1} \Delta y_{t-(k-1)} + u_t \quad (3)$$

Where

$$\lambda = (\sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i) - I_g \text{ and } T_i = (\sum_{i=1}^i \beta_i) - I_g$$

3.2.3 Equilibrium/Error Correction Model Estimates

Equilibrium/Error Correction attempts to estimate the equilibrium long run relationships between study variables after adjusting for short run distortions. Nwakanma et al (2014) as well as Brooks (2009) argue that ECM is valuable for policy purposes as it provides an estimate of the speed with which the time series variables adjust back to equilibrium after short run distortions.

3.2.4 Granger Causality Tests

The Standard Granger Causality test seeks to evaluate the extent to which variations in a dependent variable say Y , are traced to variations in explanatory variable, say X and further, whether the addition of previous or lagged values of X can, improve the explanation of Y . in this circumstance, a time series variable Y is said to be Granger Caused by X if X assists in the explanation of Y and also, if the resulting coefficients of Lagged X are found to be statistically significant and vice versa.

Accordingly, Brooks (2009), Maddala (2007) as well as Gujarati and Porter (2009) show that the general premise of Granger Causality formulation could be expressed in equations (5) and (6) below:

Where Y_t and X_t are the series under evaluation, u_t and V_t represent the idiosyncratic or white noise errors, which embody all the variations in the series Y_t and X_t that are not incorporated in the lagged values. In all, maximum lag length stipulated is only 2.

Results

For purpose of clarity this section is discussed under the following sub-sections:

4.1 Presentation of Results of Stationarity Test

The results of the Stationarity test are presented in table 2 below:

Table 2: Stationarity Test Results:

Differenced variables	ADF - Statistic	Mackinnon's Test Critical Values			Order of integration
		1%	5%	10%	
D (GDP)	-4.177148	-3.808546	-3.020686	-2.650413	1(1)
D(FAF)	-6.214283	-3.788030	-3.012363	-2.646119	1(1)
D(FMQ)	-4.175055	-3.788030	-3.012363	-2.646119	1(1)
D(FMF)	-5.255974	-3.808546	-3.020686	-2.650413	1(1)
D(FRC)	-6.834374	-3.788030	-3.012363	-2.646119	1(1)
D(TGC)	-4.843459	-3.808546	-3.020686	-2.650413	1(1)

D(GDP), D(FAF), D(FMQ), D(FMF) D(FRC) and D(TGC) represent differenced variants of the study variables

Source: Authors' Computations Using E -views 7.1

The results of stationarity test shown in table 2 above indicate that the absolute values of the ADF test statistics for the variables of study are all higher than their respective Mackinnon test critical values at 1%, 5% and 10%. Further the variables of study are all stationary at first difference. Consequently, and in accordance with the decision rule for stationarity test, it is concluded that all the study variables are stationary and therefore, qualify for employment in estimating the Johansen's multivariate co-integration equation.

4.2 Presentation of Johansen's Co-integration Results

The results of Johansen's Co-integration analysis are presented in table 3 below;

Table 3: Johansen's Co-integration Test Results:

Obs.	Series	Hypothesized Noof CE(S)	Eigen Value	Trace Statistics	0.05 Critical Value	Prob. **
21	D(GDP)	None *	0.999239	350.7613	95.75366	0.0000
	D(FAF)	At most 1*	0.988973	199.9536	69.81889	0.0000
	D(FMQ)	At most 2*	0.941516	105.2982	47.85613	0.0000
	D(FMF)	At most 3*	0.653345	45.67934	29.79707	0.0004
	D(FRC)	At most 4*	0.546315	23.43139	15.49471	0.0026
	D(FTC)	At Most 5	0.277785	6.834010	8.841466	0.0889

Trace statistics indicates 5 cointegrating equations at 0.05 level.

* Denotes rejection of null hypothesis at 0.05 level,

** Denotes Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis(1999) P-values.

Source: Authors' Computations Using E-views 7.1

The results of Johansen's cointegration analysis shown in table 3 above indicate the prevalence of five (5 no) cointegrating equations (Trace statistic > 0.05 critical value). The probability levels of the five co-integrating equations which are all significant at 0.05 level confirms prevalence of significant long run relationship in Nigeria, among classified sectoral microcredit allocations under study and gross domestic product.

4.3 Presentation of Error Correction Estimates

The results of Error Correction estimates are presented in table 4 below:

Table 4: Error Correction Estimates

Dependent Variable: (DGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Sample (Adjusted): 1993-2014

Included Observations: 22 after Adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FAF)	-5323.411	1045.809	-5.090231	0.0001
D(FMQ)	-59087.13	6824.683	-8.657857	0.0017
D(FMF)	28430.39	4366.524	6.510989	0.0000
D(FRC)	12473.32	1279.793	9.746360	0.0000
D(FTC)	721.1285	156.5501	4.606376	0.0003
ECM(-1)	-0.658909	0.222428	2.962351	0.0092
R-squared	0.762352	Mean dependent Var		17303066
Adj. R-squared	0.751279	S.D. dependent Var		20854904
S.E. of Regress	3445319	Akaike Info criterion		33.16993
S.S. resid.	1.90E+14	Schwarz criterion		33.46749
Log likelihood	-358.8693	Hannan-Quinn		33.24003
Durbin-Watson Stat.	1.874184			
F-Statistic	89.90994			
Prob (f-Statistic)	0.0000			

Source: Authors' Computations Using E-views 7.1

The Error Correction Estimates in table 4 above indicate that in the long run and after adjusting for short run distortions, variations in the study's explanatory variables explain 76.23 percent of changes in Nigeria's GDP.

Table 4 further confirms long run sensitivities of Nigeria's GDP to variations in microcredit allocations to Agricultural/Forestry, other Mining/Quarrying, other Manufacturing/Food processing, Real estate/Construction and Transport/General Commerce as -5323.411, -59087.13, 28430.39, 12473.32 and 721.1285 respectively. They are all significant at 0.05 level. Further, the ECM has the expected negative sign with an overall line of fit which is significant at 0.0000 level. The Durbin Watson value of 1.874184 is within acceptable range. The absolute value of ECM coefficient is 65.891 percent. It implies that about 65.891 percent of estimated disequilibrium in Nigeria's gross domestic product is approximately offset by short-term adjustments in microcredit allocations to the classified sectors of the economy annually. On the whole, the ECM coefficient has an associated probability value of 0.0092, which significant at 0.05 level.

4.4 Presentation of Standard Pair-Wise Granger Causality Test Results: The results of the Granger Causality test executed are presented in table 5 below;

Table 5: Results of Pair-Wise Granger Causality Test:

Null Hypothesis	Obs.	F-Statistic	Prob.
D(FAF) does not Granger Cause D(GDP)	21	0.09494	0.9099
D(GDP) does not Granger Cause D(FAF)	21	3.09029	0.0733
D(FMQ) does not Granger Cause D(GDP)	21	1.24661	0.3039
D(GDP) does not Granger Cause D(FMQ)	21	3.46007	0.0564
D(FMF) does not Granger Cause D(GDP)	21	0.03725	0.9635
D(GDP) does not Granger Cause D(FMF)	21	7.73747	0.0045
D(FRC) does not Granger Cause D(GDP)	21	3.07305	0.0742
D(GDP) does not Granger Cause D(FRC)	21	4.19095	0.0344
D(FTC) does not Granger Cause D(GDP)	21	6.90982	0.0069
D(GDP) does not Granger Cause D(FTC)	21	29.4681	4.E-06

Source: Authors' Computations Using E -views 7.1

The Pair-Wise Standard Granger Causality test results shown in table 5 above indicates that there is no significant causal relationship between Nigeria's GDP and each of microcredit allocations to agriculture/forestry and other mining/quarrying. However, uni-directional causalities are observed to prevail significantly between Nigeria's GDP and each of micro-financing allocations to manufacturing/food processing and real estate/construction with causality flowing from GDP to each of micro-financing allocations to manufacturing/food processing and real estate/construction respectively. On the whole, significant bi-directional causalities are observed between Nigeria's GDP and micro-financing allocated to transport and general commerce with each reinforcing or promoting the other thereby, enjoying a significant level of contemporaneous relationship.

5.0 Discussions, Conclusions and Policy Recommendations:

The results of Johansen's co-integration and Error Correction Estimates provide evidence of hope that microcredit operations significantly relate to Nigeria's economic growth even in the long run. Further, the Granger Causality results show evidences of concrete progress in the history of the influence of associated bank credits on Nigeria's economic growth. While for agriculture/forestry as well as other mining and quarrying, there is presently, no significant causality in any direction, the results for other manufacturing/food processing as well as real estate/construction which provide evidence of un-directional causal relationships with causality flowing from the economy to those sectors (demand-following) are to say the least, encouraging. In effect, developments in the economy provide business opportunities for micro-financing institutions to lend to these two sectors which however, provide hope for future mutual relationship between those two sectors and Nigeria's economy. Of greatest significance is the fact that a contemporaneous relationship prevails between Nigeria's economy and micro-financing allocated to the transport/general commerce sector over the period of study. On the whole, the results of this study provide compelling evidence to assert that Nigeria's microcredit institutions are becoming more relevant in Nigeria's economic progress. This is demonstrated by the prevailing significant bi-directional relationship between Nigeria's GDP and transport/general commerce sector, as well as the significant uni-directional relationships between GDP and other manufacturing/food processing and real estate/construction. In this sense, the results of this study represent an improvement over those of Duada (2007) in which the community banking system which was then supposed to champion microcredit disbursements to priority sectors unfortunately concentrated over 70% of its credits allocations to the juicy general commerce sector.

From the above, it is concluded that (i) Nigeria's microcredit operations have gained significance for long run policy considerations and implementation (ii) Microcredit operations in Nigeria have expanded their influences from the traditional transport/general commerce sector to other more sustainable sectors which include real estate and construction and other manufacturing/food processing (iii) it is likely that these expansions in influence will continue in the nearest future to cover agriculture/forestry as well as other mining/quarrying.

In the light of the results of this study, it is recommended that;

- (i) Micro-financing institutions should invest increased resources in the development of more micro deposit as well as microcredit products with sector specific qualities or characteristics.
- (ii) Micro-financing institutions should be exempted from payment of state and local government levies. Further, they should be made to pay relatively lower after-tax profits in order to improve on their operating financial resources and be able to fund the intermediation process in the communities at micro levels.

References

- Adeyemi, K. S. (2007). Institutional Reforms for Efficient Microfinance Operations in Nigeria Union Digest, Vol. 11, Nos. 3 & 4, pp. 10-27.
- Agene, C. A. (2011). Microfinance Banking: Principles and Practice, Ibadan, Daily Graphics, p.3.
- Adewunmi, W. (ed), Rural Banking in Nigeria, Essex, Longman/Nigerian Institute of Bankers, pp. 25-31. Ajeje, H. C. Ezi, C. T., Akekere, J. and Ewubare, D. B. (2006). Financial Institutions, Markets and Contemporary Issues, Port Harcourt, Pearl Publishers, pp. 20-21.
- Akinboyo, O. L. (2007). Microfinance Banks: Unlocking The Potentials of Micro Business Activities of The Nigerian Rural Economy, The Bullion, Vol. 31, No.1, (Jan/March) pp. 39-51.
- Akosile, A. 1. and Ajayi, O. A. (2014). The Impact of Microfinance Institutions on Poverty Reduction in Nigeria, European Journal of Business and Management, Vol. 6, No. 35, pp.1-7.
- Aliero, H. M. Abdullahi, Y.Z. and Adamu, N. (2013). Private Sector Credit and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria: An Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound Approach, Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, Vol. 4, No.1, (Jan), pp. 83-90, Doi:10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n1p83.
- Brooks, C. (2009). Introductory Econometrics for Finance, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 318-375; 311312.
- Crowley, J. (2008). Credit Growth in the Middle East, North Africa and Central Asia Region, IMF Working Paper, No. 08/184.
- Dauda, R. O. S. (2007). The Role of Community Banking System in Nigeria's Development Process: An Appraisal, Journal of Banking, Vol. 2, No. 1, Pp. 82 —103.

- Demetriades, P. O. and Hussein, K. (1996). Does Financial Development Cause Economic Growth? Time Series Evidence from 16 Countries, *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 51, pp. 387— 411.
- Ezirim, C. B., Adebajo, R. U. and Ogunbiyi, S.S. (2008). Micro Finance and Rural. Economic Development: Some Theoretical Issues, in Nwikina, C.G. and Mawo, J.G. (ed), *Microfinance and Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria, Strategies and Challenges*, Port Harcourt, Harrisco Press, pp 1-22.
- Goldsmith, R. W. (1969). *Financial Structure and Development*, New Haven, Econometrics, Boston, McGraw Hill, pp. 762 -787.
- Helms, B. (2006). *Access for All: Building Inclusive Financial Systems*, Consultative Group to Assist the Poor, Washington, World Bank.
- Idachaba, F. S. (1994). The Second Coming of Commodity Boards in Nigeria: Curse or Blessing? in Ijere, M. O. and Ayoola, G.B. (ed), *Commodity Boards In A Liberalized Economy*, Nsukka, Falladu Publishing Coy, pp. 14 - 28.
- Ibene, A. (1981). Banks Have No Cause to Complain On Rural Banking Scheme, *Business Times*, (April 20), p. 26.
- Jaiyeola, A.J.O. (2012). *Banking as Public Good: The Nigerian Challenge*. A Valedictory Paper by the President and Chairman of Council, the Chartered Institute of Bankers, Nigeria.
- Josee, V. M., Karemu, G., Kanchori, D. and Okibo, B.W. (2014). Role of Social Media Networks in Penetration of International Markets by Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya: A Case of Small Businesses at Yaya Centre, Nairobi County, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(26), 1-6.
- Maddala, G. S. (2007). *Introduction to Econometrics*, New Delhi, John Willey, pp. 557-570; 379-380. McKinnon, R.I. (1973). *Money and Capital in Economic Development*, Washington D.C., Brookings Institute.
- Murty, K. S., Sailaja, K. and Demissie, W. M. (2012). The Long-Run Impact of Bank Credit on Economic Growth in Ethiopia: Evidence from The Johansen's Multivariate Co-Integration Approach, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 4, No. 14, pp. 20-33.
- Nnamdi, I. S. and Nwakanma, P. C. (2011). *Marketing of Financial Services in Nigeria: Theory and Developments*, Owerri, Strammac Communications Consult, pp. 166- 185.
- Nnamdi, I.S. and Nwiyordee, A.N. (2014). Private Sector Microcredit Programmes, Financial Inclusion and Sectoral Entrepreneurship: Evidence and Insights from Nigeria, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 6, No. 35, pp. 204 -214.
- Nnamdi, I. S & Lenne, L. T., (2015). Microcredit in Nigeria's economic growth Process; a multi-sectoral analysis. *Nigerian Journal of Financial Research*, 10(1). Pp, 1 – 13.
- Nwakanma, P.C., Nnamdi, I.S. and Omojefe, G.O. (2014). From Rural to Micro Finance Banking: Contributions of Microcredits to Nigeria's Economic Growth -An ARDL Approach, *International Journal of Financial Research*, Vol. 5, No.3, (July), pp. 73-85, doi:10.5430/ijfr.v5n3p73.
- Nwankwo, G.O. (1985). *The Nigerian Financial System*, London Macmillan Press, pp. 95-98.

- Nuno, C. L. (2012). Bank Credit and Economic Growth: A Dynamic Panel Data Analysis. *The Economic Research Guardian*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 256-267.
- Okafor, F. O. (2011). Fifty Years of Banking Sector Reforms in Nigeria (1960 - 2010): Past Lessons-Future Imperatives, Enugu, Ezu Books, pp. 44-45.
- Okpara, G. C. (2010). Microfinance Banks and Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria, *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, Vol. 12, No. 6, pp.177 -191.
- Olashore, O. (1983). Rural Banking: Strategies and Policies of the Government and the Central Bank of Nigeria, In Osuntogun, A. and Adewunmi, W. (ed), *Rural Banking In Nigeria*, Essex, Longman/Nigerian Institute of Bankers, pp. 72-80.
- Oyatoye, E.T.O. (1983). The Nigerian Banking System and Credit Needs for Rural Development.
- Patrick, H.T. (1976). Demand Following or Supply Leading Finance, in Meier, G.M. (ed), *Leading Issues in Economic Development*, New York, Oxford University Press, pp. 296-299.
- Remenyi, J. and Quinones, B. (2000). *Microfinance and Poverty Alleviation: Case Studies from Asia and the Pacific*, New York, Pinter.
- Robinson, M. S (2001). *The Microfinance Revolution: Sustainable Finance for the Poor*, New York/Washington, Open Society/World Bank, pp.138-149.
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1934). *The Theory of Economic Development*, Cambridge, Mass, Harvard University Press.
- Shaw, E. S. (1973). *Financial Deepening In Economic Development*, London, Oxford University Press.
- Shaw, E.S. (1976). Financial Repression and Liberalization, In Meier, G.M. (ed), *Leading Issues In Economic Development*, New York, Oxford University Press, pp. 305 — 310.
- Sharma, G. L. and Puri, H. (2013). An Empirical Testing of Relationship Between Microfinance and Economic Growth in India, *Journal of Indian Research*, Vol. 1, No. 2, (April—June), pp. 87-94.
- Umesi, R. (1981). Bank Complain About Rural Banking Scheme, *Business Times*, (April 6), p. 1.
- Umoh, P. N. (1984). Financial Development And the Rural Banking Scheme in Nigeria, *The Banker*, Vol. 134, No. 703, London, Institute of Bankers, (Sept), pp. 74-81.
- Yunus, M. (2003). *Banker to the Poor: Micro Lending and the Battle against World Poverty*, New York, Public Affairs.
- Yale University Press. Gujarati, D. N. and Porter, D.C. (2009). Basic Yunus, M. (2008). *Creating a World without Poverty: Social Business and the Future of Capitalism*, New York, Public Affairs.